
European Standardisation Panel Survey

Multiple Service Framework Contract

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Lot 3 - Studying, assessing and evaluating research and innovation programmes and policies (SARI)
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Presentation of results and recommendations
within the StandICT Academy Webinar
on Research and Standardisation

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Agenda

- Objectives
- Implementation of the survey
- Results
- Recommendations

Objectives

- Develop and implement a European Standardisation Panel Survey (ESPS) to generate a database to allow an analysis in order to help **identify industry's demand for standards as potential results of R&I projects**, to contribute to the **assessment of how EU R&I framework programmes tackle the standardisation needs of industry**, and to contribute raising awareness on the **importance of standardisation in general and its interface with R&I for industry**.
 - To design a **large-scale survey** to collect data on the standardisation activities and needs of EU companies in general and related to R&I based standardisation and standards in particular.
 - Analysis of current activities and future trends in relation of the **demand and use of R&I based standards** for use by all stakeholders involved in standardisation, incl. R&I policy makers and any other interested parties.
 - Develop **strategies for the involvement of R&I actors in European and international standardisation by matching the supply of R&I based standards with the demand of industry**. Contribute to **understand the integration of R&I results in standardisation processes, the implementation of standards, and the effects of standardisation and standards on entrepreneurial and commercial success**. Develop **policies for the involvement of R&I actors in European and international standardisation**, with a special view on the potential role of R&I results in formulating mandates by the EC addressing the ESOs.
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Implementation of the Survey

- Questionnaire reflects both the insights from the literature, the experience collected within the performance of the German Standardisation Panel, the objectives of the project, and the feedback received from the EC and collected from industry experts and the presidential committee of CEN-CENELEC, and ETSI.
- Distribution of the ESPS started at the World Standard's Day, **October 14, 2023**
- Following a letter by Elena Santiago Cid, Director General of the European Committee for Standardisation, to all members of CEN-CENELEC, i.e., the national SDOs in the EU Member States, but also the other 16 European countries, a webinar in collaboration with CCMC has been organised on October 30.
- Another webinar with SBS has been organised on November 16. Finally, the ESPS has been distributed among the networks of the Horizon Europe projects StandICT, HSBooster, and Stand4EU.
- Participants of Horizon 2020 and Horizon Europe projects been surveyed in the context of the scoping study for developing the Code of Practice on standardisation have been invited.
- In Germany, the link to the German version of the ESPS, the German Standardisation Panel, has been sent to more than 30,000 experts starting after October 14, 2023.

Characteristics of the Sample

- most respondents work in R&D, executive management, standardisation and quality management
- two thirds of the headquarters are located in Germany
- mechanical engineering, electrotechnical engineering and chemical sectors are most prominent industries, but also experts from the public sector responded
- more than 50% perform R&D and have introduced product or process innovations
- normal distribution of age, but more than 60% are above 50, and less than 15% female

Relevance of research results for standard development

- own research, customers' requirements and policy or regulation are most important inputs for standardisation
- for industry requirements from customers and suppliers are more important than for the remaining respondents
- research is most important for measurement and testing standards, followed by quality, environmental, interoperability and health standards
- most important advantages: free access to scientific insights and keeping track with scientific and technical progress; for industry more important than for the remaining respondents: leveraging own research results via standards for the development of own product and process innovation and preventing that competing research content become dominant designs
- most important disadvantages: in general of low relevance, only little support from other companies/stakeholders relevant for industry

Approaches to integrate research results as input for standard development and their expected impacts

- most important is increasing knowledge about the effects of standardisation in HEIs and PROs, more involvement of companies in publicly funded research projects, and more funding of standardisation as means of exploitation (knowledge valorisation) in EU projects; industry favours including standardisation into tax incentive regimes for research and development
- most relevant impacts of standards based on research results as input on innovation are faster or easier access to European or international markets favoured by industry, but also higher confidence in innovative products and processes among consumers and wider use of recognised methodologies, processes

Organisations' engagement in standardisation

- **Most important needs in order to increase companies' engagement in standardisation activities**
 - comprehensive overview of and easy access to existing standards
 - easier access to standardisation activities and committees
 - missing awareness of the benefits, limited resources, and funding
 - faster and less bureaucratic standardisation processes
 - more recognition for contributors
- **Approaches to help companies increasing competitiveness through strengthening their standard-setting capabilities**
 - participation in standardisation should follow strategic approach
 - standardisation processes should be timely
 - close alignment of the produced standards with the regulatory framework

Organisations' engagement in standardisation

- **Companies' needs for a better implementation of standardisation through cooperation between industry and science**
 - for closer cooperation with research in standardisation, HEIs, and PROs should increase their knowledge, capacity, and incentives
 - companies' capabilities to get effectively involved in standardisation must also be strengthened
 - communication capacities to support census-finding processes and exploit opportunities for interdisciplinary collaboration to develop comprehensive and easily implementable standards
 - sharing of data and research findings supported by open science and open access
 - continuous monitoring and feedback from scientific partners to ensure that standards are at the cutting edge of technology but also cost-effective
 - reflecting the needs of SMEs particularly
 - all these approaches together will help improve collaboration in standardisation, which eventually contributes to technical progress and innovation.

Summary of the survey results

- Customers' requirements and regulations, as well as inputs from their own research, most relevant sources for standard development
- Research input most important for measurement and testing standards, followed by quality and environmental standards
- Most significant advantage of research as input for standardisation is free access to scientific content and ability to keep track of scientific progress
- Challenges are missing support from other organisations, particularly companies, and prematurity of research results as input for standards

Final recommendations

- General recommendations
- Recommendations addressing industry
- Recommendations addressing HEIs and PROs
- Recommendations addressing SDOs
- Recommendations addressing research funding organisations
- Recommendations for other areas of innovation policy

General recommendations

- *Including standardisation into the definition of R&D and innovation*
 - It is recommended that the comprehensive integration of standardisation is discussed in the upcoming revisions of the OECD Frascati and Oslo manuals.
- *Improve measurement*
 - It is recommended to develop indicators and evaluation systems to help the experts being active in standardisation to show their contributions to the performance of their organisation.
- *Standardisation strategies aligned with R&D*
 - It is recommended that all types of organisations develop standardisation strategies aligned with their R&D strategies.
- *Demographic challenge for standardisation experts*
 - It is recommended to HEIs expand their education and training activities on standardisation.

Recommendations addressing industry

■ *Raising awareness*

- It is recommended to increase awareness within companies of the benefits of participating in standardisation in general and of the coordination with research.

■ *Resources for standardisation contributing to shaping regulatory frameworks*

- It is recommended to provide adequate resources for standardisation activities to exploit the opportunities of research but also direct future regulatory developments.

■ *Specific focus on SMEs*

- It is recommended that research-active SMEs join standardisation, because they benefit from research-driven standardisation, e.g., by keeping track of scientific and technical progress, but also to leverage their own research results for the development of their own innovative products including improving their quality.

Recommendations addressing HEIs and PROs

■ *Raising awareness*

- It is recommended to increase awareness about the relevance of standardisation.

■ *Resources for standardisation*

- It is recommended to provide adequate funding opportunities.

■ *Performance indicators*

- It is recommended to develop and establish performance indicators, which reach a similar acceptance as scientific publications and patents.

■ *Education about standardisation*

- It is recommended that HEIs expand their education and training activities on standardisation particularly approaching female students to address the gender imbalance and the forthcoming demographic change.

Recommendations addressing SDOs

■ *Standardisation processes*

- It is recommended to increase agility of standardisation processes to allow timely release of standards.

■ *Service portfolio*

- It is recommended to expand the service portfolios for R&I actors and examine new ways to align their activities with R&I, particularly appreciated by smaller research-active organisations.

■ *Awareness of products*

- It is recommended to increase the limited awareness of workshop agreements, whose impact is similarly assessed like those of standards.

■ *Open source software (OSS) and hardware (OSH)*

- It is recommended to consider explicitly OSS and OSH within IPR policies, but also closer collaboration with OS communities to speed up an increase agility, and integrate research-performing SMEs.

■ *Monitoring implementation of standards*

- It is recommended to monitor the implementation of research-based standards to collect feedback to for revising existing standards to maintain a stock of standards promoting firms' competitiveness.
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Recommendations addressing research funding organisations

■ *Funding at the European level*

- It is recommended to establish new funding schemes or continue and expand the financial support for standardisation as a means of exploitation, i.e., knowledge valorisation, of research results generated within the framework programmes.

■ *Funding at the level of Member States*

- It is recommended to continue or expand existing funding programmes to align with national research programmes and Member States without similar funding programmes to establish them.

■ *HEIs and PROs*

- It is recommended to consider HEIs and PROs in the public funding schemes explicitly since they are lacking in knowledge about standardisation and, therefore, insufficiently represented in standardisation activities.

■ *Smaller organisations*

- It is recommended to consider smaller organisations in the support programmes on standardisation as knowledge valorisation to offer appropriate services because of their higher need for support from SDOs in integrating research results into standardisation.

Recommendations for other areas of innovation policy

- *Including standardisation into the definition of R&D and innovation*
 - It is recommended of discussing standardisation to integrate in the upcoming revisions of the OECD Frascati and Oslo manuals to allow the development of indicators and evaluation systems.
- *Research tax credit*
 - It is recommended expand the tax base to expenditures for standardisation because in research tax credit system, in particular, smaller organisations confirm its effectiveness.
- *Research and innovation funding programmes*
 - It is suggested to consider standardisation in further research and innovation related support programmes targeting SMEs.
- *Regulation*
 - It is recommended that ex ante regulatory impact assessments should screen the existing standards to use the already existing scientific evidence base and avoid contradictions.
- *Public procurement*
 - It is recommended to consider the role of research-based standards in updating the public procurement directive, but also in the relevant EU funding programmes.

Summary of recommendations

- Challenges:
 - different stakeholders are addressed
 - various levels are addressed
 - various strategy and policy areas are addressed
 - therefore, coordination of stakeholders and instruments across various levels are needed

Next steps

- Discussion with EC DG RTD about possible next steps
- Discussion with DIN about continuing the German Standardisation Panel in May
- Discussion with other NSBs about multilateral collaboration with the German Standardisation Panel!

Contacts and Links

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- Link to full report
by Knut Blind, Luzie Kromer, Peter Neuhäusler,
Daniele Rosenberg & Torben Schubert

<https://op.europa.eu/en/publication-detail/-/publication/d5c4f1a7-e75e-11ee-9ea8-01aa75ed71a1/language-en/format-PDF/source-310773886>

